

FREE EDGE STRESS REDUCTION VIA VARIATION
OF FIBER VOLUME FRACTION

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ABSTRACT

An effective method to reduce the free edge interlaminar stresses in a symmetric laminate under uniform axial extension is presented. Pseudo three—dimensional finite element method is employed to calculate the interlaminar stresses. The reduction of the interlaminar stresses is achieved by varying the fiber volume fraction near the free edge. Numerical results show that the interlaminar normal and shear stresses near the free edges can be significantly reduced or even totally eliminated by the proposed technique.

KEYWORDS: Composite laminate; Free edge; Interlaminar stress; Fiber content; Matrix.

1. INTRODUCTION

Because of its high strength and stiffness to weight ratios, fiber reinforced composite materials have been widely used in aeronautical industries to replace metal in the aircraft structures for the purpose of weight saving. But to use them efficiently a good understanding of their structural behaviors under various loading conditions is needed. One important issue to the laminated composite material is free edge delamination under loading in the plane of the laminate. This type of delamination may cause failures at loads well below the design loads.

Pipes and Pagano (1) used finite difference procedure to solve the reduced form of three—dimensional elasticity equations for a symmetric laminate under uniform axial extension. Their results show that the interlaminar stresses near the free—edge region

are much higher than the stresses in the other regions. They also suggested that a possible stress singularity exists at the free edge. Later on numerous investigations (2-8) have been conducted to study this high stress field near free edges using either finite different, finite element, or some other techniques. Same conclusions are obtained that the delamination is caused by very high interlaminar stresses due to mismatch of elastic properties between layers, and the width of this high stress region is approximately equal to the laminate thickness.

The strength of the structure will be greatly reduced if delaminations occur. Hence, the initiation of delamination should be prevented or the high interlaminar stresses near free edge should be reduced. In order to achieve this goal, several methods have been proposed in recent years. Kim (9), Heyliger & Reddy (10), and Howard et al. (11,12) used free edge cap reinforcement to minimize the intensity of the high stresses. Vizzini (13) in 1987 used structural tailoring technique, i.e., edge alteration, to prevent the free edge delamination. Other techniques used to prevent delamination or reduce the free-edge stresses include using adhesive layers (14), stitching along the free edges (15), and altering the stacking sequence of the laminates (16).

The purpose of this paper is to propose a different approach for the reduction of the free edge interlaminar stresses. The approach is to vary fiber volume fraction near free edges which in turn to minimize the mismatch of elastic properties between adjacent layers, and consequently reduce the interlaminar stresses.

2. FORMULATION

Consider a long, symmetric laminate subjected to uniform axial extension in the x -direction as shown in Fig. 1. The laminate with width $2b$ and thickness $2h$ is assumed to be long in the x -direction. The displacement field of this laminate in any $x = \text{constant}$ plane is given by (1):

$$\begin{aligned} u(x, y, z) &= \epsilon_0 x + U(y, z) \\ v(x, y, z) &= V(y, z) \\ w(x, y, z) &= W(y, z) \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where ϵ_0 is the applied uniform axial strain. Because of the symmetry about x - y plane and antisymmetry about x - z plane, only one quadrant of the laminate cross-section is needed to be considered. The corresponding symmetric boundary conditions are

$$\begin{aligned} U(0, z) = V(0, z) = W(y, 0) &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial U(y, 0)}{\partial z} = \frac{\partial V(y, 0)}{\partial z} = \frac{\partial W(0, z)}{\partial y} &= 0 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

In addition, the traction free conditions on the edges and surfaces give

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_y = \tau_{yz} = \tau_{xy} = 0 & \quad \text{at} \quad y = \pm b \\ \sigma_z = \tau_{yz} = \tau_{xz} = 0 & \quad \text{at} \quad z = \pm h \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

2.1 Finite Element Model The laminate considered in this study is assumed to be long enough in the x -direction so that the state of stress and strain away from the ends of the plate is independent of position along the x -axis. Hence the analysis can be restricted to y - z plane (Fig. 1). For the finite element model, a modified two-dimensional plain strain element such as eight-noded quadrilateral, isoparametric element with three degrees of freedom per node is used for the analysis.

In this generalized two-dimensional plain strain element, the strain field based on Eq. (1) can be expressed as

$$\{\epsilon\}_t = \{\epsilon\} + \{\epsilon\}_o \quad (4)$$

where $\{\epsilon\}_o$ is defined as

$$\{\epsilon\}_o = \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_o \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

and $\{\epsilon\}$ is the conventional strain vector which can be related to the nodal displacement vector, $\{q\}$, by

$$\{\epsilon\} = [B] \{q\} \quad (6)$$

Assuming there is no other external loads on the element except ϵ_o , then the total potential energy is equal to the strain energy of the element or

$$\pi = \frac{1}{2} \int_V \{\epsilon\}_t^T [D] \{\epsilon\}_t dv \quad (7)$$

Substituting Eqs. (4) to (6) into Eq. (7), the potential energy becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \pi = \frac{1}{2} \{q\}^T \left(\int_V [B]^T [D] [B] dv \right) \{q\} + \frac{1}{2} \{q\}^T \left(\int_V [B]^T [D] \{\epsilon\}_o dv \right) + \\ \frac{1}{2} \left(\int_V \{\epsilon\}_o^T [D] [B] dv \right) \{q\} + \frac{1}{2} \int_V \{\epsilon\}_o^T [D] \{\epsilon\}_o dv \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Minimizing the potential energy with respect to the nodal displacement provides the equilibrium statement for the system, or

$$\left(\int_V [B]^T [D] [B] dv \right) \{q\} = - \int_V [B]^T [D] \{\epsilon\}_o dv \quad (9)$$

or, in short,

$$[K]\{q\} = \{F\} \quad (10)$$

where $[K]$ is the stiffness matrix and $\{F\}$ is the load vector due to ϵ_0 .

2.2 Variation of Fiber volume Fraction The variation of fiber volume fraction (C_f) considered in this study is described in this section. The fiber volume fraction in a ply of the laminate is usually uniformly distributed over its entire width. In order to reduce the free-edge stresses, however, it is assumed that the fiber volume fraction near free edge of a ply is varied linearly in the y -direction in according to the following expressions

$$\begin{aligned} C_f &= C_o && \text{for } y \leq y_o \\ C_f &= C_e + \frac{b-y}{b-y_o} (C_o - C_e) && \text{for } b > y > y_o \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

in which C_o is the original fiber volume fraction and is set to be 0.6; C_e is the fiber volume fraction at free edge; y_o is the location where the fiber volume fraction begins to vary.

2.3 Effective Material Properties of the Laminate Since the fiber volume fraction is varied near the free edge of the laminate, the corresponding engineering constants will vary accordingly. In this study, the formulas used for the calculation of these effective engineering constants are based on the composite cylinders model and the three phase cylinder model.

The basic material properties for a graphite/epoxy laminate are taken from Ref. 17. The particular numerical values are :

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Elastic moduli:} & \quad E_{f1} = 24 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & \quad E_{f2} = 2 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} \\ & \quad E_m = 0.6 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} \\ \text{Poisson's ratio:} & \quad \nu_f = \nu_m = 0.3 \end{aligned}$$

where the subscripts f and m refer to the fiber and matrix; 1 and 2 refer to the fiber and transverse directions, respectively.

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

The problems to be considered in the present study are four-layer symmetric laminates subject to a uniform in-plane strain, ϵ_0 , in the x -direction. The $[0/90]_s$ and $[\pm 45]_s$ laminates which have been studied extensively in the analysis of the free edge problem are chosen for the analysis. The width to the thickness ratio of the laminate is taken to be 10 and the applied initial strain ϵ_0 is set to 0.001 in all analyses.

The finite element mesh for a quadrant of the laminate cross-section contains total 1013 nodes and 310 elements. The size of the elements near the interface and free edge

region is much smaller than that in the remote region. All stresses in the following discussion are at the interface of the two plies and are plotted in the region near the free edge where the interlaminar stresses are significant.

Four different fiber volume fraction (C_e) at the free edge are studied. The location of y_0 is either $0.9b$. The four different C_e are 0.0, 0.2, 0.4, and 0.6. When $C_e = 0.6$, it is the case that C_f is not varied in a ply.

3.1 Cross-ply $[0/90]_s$ Laminates In cross-ply laminates, interlaminar stresses σ_z and τ_{yz} are significant. Figs. 2-7 show the σ_z and τ_{yz} stress distributions. Fig. 2 shows the σ_z -distribution with C_f varied in 0° ply only. It is found that σ_z appears to be singular at the free edge in all cases. However, decreasing C_f near the free edge in 0° ply results in increasing σ_z at the free edge. This is due to the fact that the mismatch of elastic properties between two layers near the free edge is enlarged in the y -direction by the reduction of C_f in 0° ply. Therefore, for a cross-ply laminate, the way to reduce the free edge interlaminar normal stress is to minimize the mismatch of elastic properties near the free edge in the y -direction. In other words, to reduce the stiffness near the free edge in the 90° ply or simultaneously in the both plies may decrease the free edge internaminar stresses. Fig. 3 shows the σ_z -distribution with C_f varied in 90° ply only. σ_z at the free edge is reduced more than 50% when C_e drops from 0.6 to 0.4. When C_e is further reduced, σ_z at the free edge reverses sign. Although the possible edge singularity is indicated in all cases, the significant reduction of σ_z at the free edge by the variation of C_f in 90° ply is evident from the curves. If C_f is varied in both layers, the free edge stress σ_z decreases monotonously with C_e as shown in Fig. 4. There is no stress singularity indicated for the case with $C_e = 0.0$ since the elastic properties of both layers at the free edge are identical. The magnitude of σ_z for $C_e = 0.0$ is reduced by almost an order as comparing to that for the case with $C_e = 0.6$.

The effect of the variation of C_f on the τ_{yz} is shown in Figs. 5-7. The peak value of τ_{yz} near the free edge is decreased by a noticeable amount in all cases as C_e is reduced from 0.6. Besides, reducing C_f near the free edge causes τ_{yz} to be more uniformly distributed in that region and consequently reduces the peak value of τ_{yz} . In addition, the peak in τ_{yz} -distribution curve disappears in the case of $C_e = 0.0$. It is seen that the variation of C_f in both layers will give more reduction of τ_{yz} near the free edge than that for variation of C_f in one layer only. It is also noticed that a moderate increase in τ_{yz} is found near $y = 0.9b$ where the C_f begins to vary. This may be attributed to the beginning change of elastic properties at this point and the redistribution of τ_{yz} . Nevertheless, the magnitude of τ_{yz} at this point is much smaller than the peak value of τ_{yz} when $C_e = 0.6$.

3.2 Angle-ply $[\pm 45]_s$ Laminates Results for $[\pm 45]_s$ laminates are illustrated in Figs. 8–13. The effect of C_f variation on the reduction of interlaminar stresses in $[\pm 45]_s$ laminates is even more noticeable than that in the $[0/90]_s$ laminates. As long as C_e is decreased in either one layer or both layers, σ_z and τ_{xz} is reduced accordingly. Again, stress fields are redistributed due to the reduction of C_f near the free edge.

The effect of y_0 on the reduction of the free edge stresses is negligible. Singular behavior exists in σ_z for most of the cases. But this highly localized stress can almost be completely eliminated if C_e is set to 0.0 in both layers as can be seen in Fig. 10. The average reduction of the normal stress, σ_z , at the free edge is about 35% when C_e is dropped from 0.6 to 0.4. σ_z is reduced by about 70% if C_e is further dropped to 0.2 and by about 95% when C_e becomes 0.0.

The most important interlaminar stress in angle-ply laminates is τ_{xz} which displays a possible singular behavior at the free edge as shown in Figs. 11 – 13. Similar to the case in cross-ply laminates, the only way to eliminate this stress singularity is to reduce C_e to zero simultaneously in both layers as evidenced in Fig. 13. Although it is not as significant as that for the normal stress, the reduction rate of τ_{xz} is still very impressive. For the case that C_f is varied in one layer only (either $+45^\circ$ or -45°), τ_{xz} at the free edge is reduced by about 20%, 40%, and 75% when C_e is dropped from 0.6 to 0.4, 0.2, and 0.0, respectively. If C_f is varied simultaneously in both layers, the reduction rate of τ_{xz} is about 35%, 60%, and 90% for the corresponding C_e .

4. CONCLUSIONS

The proposed technique — by varying the fiber volume fraction near free edges of a laminate — is found to be effective in the reduction of the free edge interlaminar stresses. The stress singularity at the free edge for different laminates can be avoided by the proposed technique. Although the study is only on Graphite/epoxy laminates, the technique can be used for laminates with different materials or elastic properties. The only shortcoming of this technique is the loss of a small amount of in-plane strength of the laminate. This can be remedied by increasing the original fiber volume fraction, for instance, from 0.6 to 0.61 or 0.62.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

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Fig. 1 Geometry of symmetric laminate

Fig. 2 σ_z along 0/90 interface for C_f varied in 0-ply only.

Fig. 5 τ_{yz} along 0/90 interface for C_f varied in 0-ply only.

Fig. 3 σ_z along 0/90 interface for C_f varied in 90-ply only.

Fig. 6 τ_{yz} along 0/90 interface for C_f varied in 90-ply only.

Fig. 4 σ_z along 0/90 interface for C_f varied in both plies.

Fig. 7 τ_{yz} along 0/90 interface for C_f varied in both plies.

Fig. 8 σ_z along ± 45 interface for C_f varied in +45-ply only.

Fig. 11 τ_{xz} only ± 45 interface for C_f varied in +45-ply only.

Fig. 9 σ_z along ± 45 interface for C_f varied in -45-ply only.

Fig. 12 τ_{xz} along ± 45 interface for C_f varied in -45-ply only.

Fig. 10 σ_z along ± 45 interface for C_f varied in both plies.

Fig. 13 τ_{xz} along ± 45 interface for C_f varied in both plies.

